

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABIJNA K bearing USN6SU19RD001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsAISHWARYA RAJ C V bearing USN6SU19RD002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

Dean
College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsANAND M P bearing USN6SU19RD003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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Mangalore - 574146

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsANUVINDHA A bearing USN6SU19RD004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARJUN K V bearing USN6SU19RD005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/MsASHIK RAHMAN N bearing USN6SU19RD006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/MsBENN PHILIP bearing USN6SU19RD007 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/MsDERONAJITH T K bearing USN6SU19RD008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/MsDEVIKA PAVITHRAN bearing USN6SU19RD009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsGOPIKA G S bearing USN6SU19RD010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/MsJISNA M M bearing USN6SU19RD011 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JITHU JIJU bearing USN6SU19RD012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsMANYA P bearing USN6SU19RD013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/MsR KRISHNA PRABHU bearing USN6SU19RD014 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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This is to certify that Mr/MsRAJISHA N P bearing USN6SU19RD015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VIDHUSMERA bearing USN6SU19RD016 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Renal dialysis Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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College of Allied Health Sciences
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